

Analysis of Unit Cost Differences in Routine Blood Examination with ABC Method (Activity Based Costing) At Muhammadiyah Selogiri Hospital

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 09 June 2022	Background: Routine blood examination as a supporting examination facility shows the highest demand. Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital in determining the cost of services based on the traditional cost method and has not determined the cost based on the activity-based costing (ABC) method. Methods: This research is qualitative research with a case study approach. The data analysis technique was carried out by collecting primary data through interviews, observation, and documentation. Results: The results showed that the unit cost of routine blood examination at the hospital based on the calculation of the ABC method was Rp. 327,269.
Corresponding Author: Irfan Abdurraafi	Conclusion: The unit cost value for routine blood tests calculated using the ABC method is greater than the real cost applied at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital with a difference of Rp. 147,269.
KEYWORDS: Unit cost, routine blood tests, ABC method	

I. PRELIMINARY

Hospital is a health service institution that provides complete individual health services consisting of inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services. Hospitals also function as providers of health treatment and recovery services [1]. Laboratory services are part of health services and provide support to other components of health services, including clinical laboratory services and public health laboratory services. Laboratory services are laboratory services to support healing and health recovery efforts. Clinical laboratories are an integral part of clinical pemediagnoses based on evidence-based medicine are supported through clinical laboratory examinations.

Unit cost analysis (unit cost) is a way to calculate costs for various existing needs, either in total or per unit by calculating all unit costs/cost centers or service departments and distributing them to these units [2]. Many methods can be used in calculating unit costs and the most widely used method is the Activity Based Costing (ABC) method. Routine blood tests are part of clinical laboratory examinations that doctors request in the process of making medical diagnoses, both in outpatient and inpatient cases.

Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital owns routine blood examination as a supporting examination facility, the demand for these supporting tests is the highest compared to other

clinical laboratory supporting tests. Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital is a Type D Hospital that receives referrals from many Puskesmas and Primary Clinics in the Wonogiri Regency area. The hospital determines the cost of services based on the traditional cost method and has not made a cost determination based on the ABC method.

II. METHOD

This research is qualitative research using a case study research design. This study describes the unit cost associated with routine blood tests at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital using the activity based costing method.

III. RESULT

Overview of Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital

Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital was established by the Selogiri Muhammadiyah Branch Manager who has socio-economic principles by prioritizing social principles of preaching amar ma'ruf nahi munkar and Muhammadiyah organizational development.

Overview of Laboratory Units

The laboratory unit of the Selogiri Muhamamdiyah Hospital provides a variety of laboratory services. Six analysts provide laboratory services. The profile of the tool is as follows:

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Table 1. Routine Hematology Machine Profile

Brand / type	ABX / ABX PENTRA XL80
Production year	2016
Year of installation	2017
Made in	France
Operating temperature	16 – 34° C
Voltage/frequency	100 – 240 Volt / 50 – 60 Hz
Reagent	ABX Diluent, Abx Alphalyse, ABX Cleaner, ABX Eosinofix, ABX Basolyse II
Parameter	27 parameter: WBC, RBC, PLT, HGB, MPV, HCT, PCT*, PDW*, MCV, MCH, MCHC, RDW-SD, RDW-CV, NE# & NE%, LY# & LY%, MO# & MO%, EOS# & EOS%, BAS# & BAS%, ALY# & ALY* %, LIC# & LIC* %

Number of Patient Visits

Table 2. Patient Data at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital in 2019-2021

No.	Type Service	2019	2020	2021
1	Emergency Room	14942	12801	1682
2	Outpatient	67325	55983	7163
3	Hospitalization _	-	-	-
4	VIP Class	270	125	6
5	Class I	1128	830	130
6	Class II	1587	1066	162
7	Class III	2403	2086	146
8	HCU	70	73	10
9	Neoristi	1084	1077	145
10	Operating Room	2164	1877	241
11	Maternity Room	1195	1208	150
	TOTAL	92168	77126	9835

Table 3. Laboratory Patient Data at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital in 2020

No.	Month	Laboratory Patient Data				
		SGOT	SGPT	UREA	CREAT	HEMA
1	January	46	46	94	57	754
2	February	35	35	72	72	839
3	March	32	32	60	60	817
4	April	17	17	25	25	533
5	May	18	18	35	32	545
6	June	17	16	29	29	598
7	July	13	13	68	69	598
8	August	24	22	59	61	329
9	September	10	10	72	74	634
10	October	12	13	70	72	577
11	November	17	21	59	59	488
12	December	55	56	79	80	639
	Total	296	299	722	690	7351
	Overall Total Hematology Analyzer					7351
	Total Blood Chemistry					2007

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This research was carried out at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital who underwent blood tests in 2020, which resulted in 7,351 Hematology Analyzer examination patients and 2,007 Blood Chemistry examination patients.

Unit cost analysis using Activity-based Costing (ABC) method

The unit cost calculation will be carried out using the ABC method [3]. The analysis process is as follows:

a. Direct Tracing

The costs consumed in each unit will be traced directly which will later be charged to the costs of each activity. If there is no activity, these costs will not appear. These costs will be direct, and can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. Class 1 Direct Cost Type

No.	Type of Class 1		Fee Service	Consumable goods	Tariff
	Laboratory Examination	Facility Service			
1	SGOT	Rp 13.120	Rp 6.600	Rp 13.500	Rp 33.220
2	SGPT	Rp 13.120	Rp 6.600	Rp 13.500	Rp 33.220
3	Ureum	Rp 11.910	Rp 6.600	Rp 13.500	Rp 32.010
4	Creatinin	Rp 11.910	Rp 6.600	Rp 13.500	Rp 32.010
5	Hematology Analyzer	Rp 52.040	Rp 6.600	Rp 15.000	Rp 73.640

Table 5. Class 2 Direct Cost Type

No.	Type of Class 2		Fee Service	Consumable goods	Tariff
	Laboratory Examination	Facility Service			
1	SGOT	Rp 13.120	Rp 4.400	Rp 13.500	Rp 31.020
2	SGPT	Rp 13.120	Rp 4.400	Rp 13.500	Rp 31.020
3	Ureum	Rp 11.910	Rp 4.400	Rp 13.500	Rp 29.810
4	Creatinin	Rp 11.910	Rp 4.400	Rp 13.500	Rp 29.810
5	Hematology Analyzer	Rp 52.040	Rp 4.400	Rp 15.000	Rp 71.440

Table 6. Class 3 Direct Cost Type

No.	Type of Laboratory Examination	Class 3		Consumable goods	Tariff
		Facility Service	Fee Service		
1	SGOT	Rp 13.120	Rp 2.200	Rp 13.500	Rp 28.820
2	SGPT	Rp 13.120	Rp 2.200	Rp 13.500	Rp 28.820
3	Ureum	Rp 11.910	Rp 2.200	Rp 13.500	Rp 27.610
4	Creatinin	Rp 11.910	Rp 2.200	Rp 13.500	Rp 27.610
5	Blood Chemistry Rates				Rp 112.860
	Hematology Analyzer	Rp 52.040	Rp 2.200	Rp 15.000	Rp 69.240

Direct cost for routine blood examination or Hematology Analyzer class III is Rp. 69,240 and blood chemistry examination is Rp. 112,860, then added up with overhead costs.

b. Activity center

Activities in routine blood tests and the length of time obtained based on interviews and observations can be

seen in Table 7. The total time required for one routine blood test is 65 minutes. This is following with standard operating procedures that apply at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital.

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Table 7. Activity Center Routine Blood Examination

No.	Activity Type	Hematology Analyzer		Blood Chemistry	
		Time (minutes)	Description	Time (minutes)	Description
1.	Registration	5	Number of activities	5	Number of activities
2.	Sampling	15	Number of actions	15	Number of actions
3.	Processing	15	Number of actions	15	Number of actions
4.	Examination	15	Number of actions	15	Number of actions
5.	Recording of examination results	10	Number of actions	10	Number of actions
6.	Clinical pathology doctor expertise	5	Number of actions	5	Number of actions
Total waiting time checkup result		65		65	

c. Overhead costs

Overhead costs are additional or unrelated costs that are not directly related to the business processes and production carried out. There are four categories of overhead costs: labor-related, equipment-related, space-related, and service-related. Labor-related includes employee costs such as salaries, overtime pay, transportation, side dishes, and health funds. Equipment related include tool depreciation, tool maintenance, calibration and tool repair. Space-related consists of depreciation, maintenance, and building repairs. Service-

related costs include electricity, telephone, gas, water, and cleaning costs. Overhead costs will be assigned to activities through indirect resources and direct resources, namely:

1) Indirect resources

Indirect costs come from several service units that are interrelated but are not used directly. The cost of indirect resources is the assignment of indirect costs to activities on a proportion basis. Non-functional units include non-medical units such as the board of directors and administrative staff.

Table 8. Table of Expenditures for Muhammadiyah Selogiri Hospital in 2020

Cost type	Cost of Hematology Analyzer	Cost of Blood Chemistry
Labor related		
Employee	Rp 6.334.108.548	Rp 6.334.108.548
Equipment related		
Depreciation and maintenance	Rp 434.397.503	Rp 434.397.503
Medical and non-medical equipment		
Space related		
Building depreciation and maintenance	Rp 563.335.127	Rp 563.335.127
Service related		
Electricity, telephone, water, and gas costs	Rp 512.165.497	Rp 512.165.497
Total	Rp 7.844.006.675	Rp 7.844.006.675

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The non-functional unit costs charged to the laboratory unit can be observed in Table 8. In Table 8. the indirect resources overhead costs for the Hematology Analyzer and Blood Chemistry examinations were Rp. 7,844,006,675 which was

charged to the functional unit. Furthermore, using the basis of the income proportion of each functional unit, the indirect cost will be obtained based on the proportions of Table 9.

Table 9. Proportion of Income

Functional unit	Total Income	Proportion	Indirect cost	
			by proportion (Hematology Analyzer)	by proportion (Blood Chemistry)
Inpatient	Rp 12.341.736.993	44,61%	Rp 3.499.461.009	Rp 3.499.461.009
Outpatient + emergency room	Rp 10.734.634.392	38,80%	Rp 3.043.772.082	Rp 3.043.772.082
Medical treatment	Rp 3.204.682.843	11,58%	Rp 908.677.819	Rp 908.677.819
Support	Rp 1.268.281.683	4,58%	Rp 359.617.313	Rp 359.617.313
Administration	Rp 114.543.502	0,41%	Rp 32.478.453	Rp 32.478.453
Total	Rp 27.663.879.413		Rp 7.844.006.675	Rp 7.844.006.675

After being calculated based on the proportion of income, a fee of IDR 359,617,313 will be obtained for the laboratory. The income for routine blood examinations is Rp. 359,617,313, then divided by all routine blood examinations (Hematology Analyzer) for as many as 7,351 patients so that the results are Rp. 48,921 for each routine blood examination and Blood Chemistry examinations for as many as 2,007 patients so that the results are Rp. 179,182.

2) Direct Resources

Direct resources are an indirect cost assignment to activities through a causal relationship between

the resources consumed and the activities generated [3]. This means that every routine blood examination activity creates a resource requirement, which is calculated according to the proportion of the number of examinations divided by the total number of examinations in the laboratory unit. In the period 2020, there were 7,351 Hematology Analyzer laboratory examinations and 2,007 blood chemistry tests. Then the part that is charged to the laboratory section, especially routine blood tests, is as shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Direct Resources Routine Blood Examination

Cost type	Cost in Lab for Examination Hematology Analyzer	Cost in Lab for Blood Chemistry Examination	Cost of Hematology Analyzer	Cost of Blood Chemistry Examination
<i>Labor related</i>				
Laboratory unit employee salary	Rp 179.054.768	Rp 179.054.768	Rp 104.173.455	Rp 104.173.455
<i>Equipment related</i>				
Medical device depreciation and equipment maintenance	Rp 127.151.019	Rp 127.151.019	Rp 73.976.030	Rp 73.976.030
<i>Space related</i>				
Building depreciation	Rp 14.646.732	Rp 14.646.732	Rp 8.521.419	Rp 8.521.419
<i>Service related</i>				

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Stationery fees, electricity, water, telephone, cleaning	Rp 8.632.520	Rp 8.632.520	Rp 5.022.371	Rp 5.022.371
Total	Rp 329.485.039	Rp 329.485.039	Rp 191.693.274	Rp 191.693.274

Based on the table above, the direct resources in the laboratory unit are Rp. 191,693,274 to then be divided by all routine blood tests (Hematology Analyzer) which are 7,351 patients, so that the figure is Rp. 26,977 and blood chemistry examination is

2,007 patients so that the figure is Rp. 95,512. After knowing the costs of indirect resources and direct resources, the next step is to add up the total calculated overhead costs, which can be seen in Table 11 below:

Table 11. Total Overhead

No.	Cost type	Total Hematology Analyzer	Total Blood Chemistry
1	<i>Indirect resources</i>	Rp 48.921	Rp 179.182
2	<i>Direct resources</i>	Rp 26.077	Rp 95.512
	Total	Rp 74.998	Rp 274.694

Overhead costs for routine blood examination services will be charged to each activity in the activity table.

each activity in the laboratory unit. Charges to the activity center are as follows:

d. Define Activity Center

According to Baker (1998) the next step in calculating unit costs using the ABC method is to assign overhead costs to

Table 12. Charges into Activity Center

No.	Activity Type	Cost Hematology Analyzer	Time (Minutes)	Cost (Blood Chemistry)	Time (Minutes)
1	Registration	Rp 15.000	5	Rp 54.939	5
2	Sampling	Rp 5.000	15	Rp 18.313	15
3	Processing	Rp 5.000	15	Rp 18.313	15
4	Examination	Rp 5.000	15	Rp 18.313	15
5	Recording of examination results	Rp 5.000	10	Rp 18.313	10
6	Clinical pathology doctor expertise	Rp 5.000	5	Rp 18.313	5
	Total	Rp 74.998		Rp 274.694	

In Table 12, the routine blood examination service time at Muhammadiyah Selogiri Hospital is 65 minutes, calculated from the patient entering the unit, until the patient leaving the laboratory unit. Meanwhile, the distribution of costs based on activities can be seen in Table 12 above.

e. Sum of Direct Cost and Overhead

The last stage is to add up the direct costs and overhead costs, which can be seen in the following table:

Table 13. Summation of Direct Costs and Overhead Costs

No.	Checking type	Total Hematology Analyzer	Total Blood Chemistry
1	<i>Direct cost</i>	Rp 26.077	Rp 95.512
2	<i>Overhead</i>	Rp 74.998	Rp 274.694
	Total	Rp 101.075	Rp 370.206

So based on the table, it can be read that the tariff based on calculations using the Activity-based Costing method for the

Hematology Analyzer examination is Rp. 101,075 and the Blood Chemistry examination is Rp. 370,206.

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Real Cost of Routine Blood Examination at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital.

The cost of routine blood examinations at the Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital to date is based on the Wonogiri Regency Regional Regulation Number 7 of 2020 concerning General Service Retribution at the Health Laboratory UPTD, namely the Hematology Analyzer examination fee of Rp. 60,000 and Blood Chemistry of Rp. 120,000.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Unit Cost of Routine Blood Examination at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital with Activity Based Costing Method. Direct costs are costs used directly to produce

health service production (costs in production units), for example, inpatient, outpatient and laboratory units [4]. Muhammadiyah Selogiri is a Hematology Analyzer examination is Rp. 101,075 and a Blood Chemistry examination is Rp. 370,206.

2. Differences in Unit Cost of Routine Blood Examination between Activity Based Costing and Real Cost Methods that that Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital has determined

In the previous table, it can be seen that the value of the tariff determined by the Activity Based Costing model has differences, namely:

Table 14. Value of Real Cost and Unit Cost of ABC model

No.	Checking type	Real cost	ABC model unit costs	Difference
1	Hematology Analyzer	Rp 60.000	Rp 101.075	Rp 41.075
2	Blood Chemistry	Rp 120.000	Rp 370.206	Rp 250.206
	The Difference in Hematology Analyzer and Blood Chemistry			Rp 209.131

Calculation of unit costs in hospitalized patients with a head injury diagnosis using the ABC method at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul obtained lower costs than the real costs and INA CBG's rates [5].

Based on the research results conducted by Syifa et al., [6] the unit cost of sterilization in the CSDD unit of PKU Muhammadiyah Bantul Hospital with the Activity Based Costing method is Rp. 2,049,388.00 with a total unit cost of one sterilization procedure averaged in CSSD units. The unit cost of ORIF Femur Fracture at the Central Surgical Installation of PKU Muhammadiyah Bantul Hospital with the Activity Based-Costing method is lower and more in line with the activity [7].

V. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATION

Conclusion

1. The unit cost of routine blood tests at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital based on the calculation of the activity-based costing (ABC) method is the Hematology Analyzer examination is Rp. 101,075 and the Blood Chemistry examination is Rp. 370,206.
2. The unit cost value for routine blood tests calculated by the Activity-Based Costing (ABC) method is greater than the real cost applied at Selogiri Muhammadiyah Hospital with the difference in the Hematology Analyzers examination, which is Rp. 41,075 and the examination of blood chemistry, which is Rp. 250,206.

Limitation

This research has several limitations in its implementation, including:

1. The data used is secondary data from hospitals in 2020 so that the results obtained are only a descriptive description of the variables studied.
2. The existing data and financial systems in hospitals have not been able to provide complete data so that some financial calculations still use assumptions in the calculations.

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